

Investigation of Possibility of Delayed Mode Contamination in Prompt Neutron Decay Constant with EFP Model

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ABSTRACT

We investigated whether the prompt neutron decay constant measured in experiments is contaminated by delayed modes. We focused on the pulsed neutron source method to estimate the reactivity of a subcritical reactor. Through numerical experiments, it was found that although the prompt neutron decay constant is slightly contaminated by the delayed mode, the error is practically negligible. To investigate the origin of the delayed mode contamination, we compared numerical results of the six-group delayed neutron precursor model and the explicit fission product model. As a result, the prompt neutron decay constant and the corresponding reactivity estimated with these models agreed with each other. This result indicates that the delayed mode contamination in the prompt neutron decay constant is likely caused by nuclides with half-life of 0.2 seconds. We also found that the models based on the same delayed neutron emission rate after a single fission reaction yields the same behavior of the number of neutrons with time.

Keywords: Reactor kinetics, Prompt neutron decay constant, Delayed neutron, Pulsed neutron source method

1. INTRODUCTION

The pulsed neutron source method[1] is one of the methods to estimate the reactivity of a subcritical reactor. In this method, pulsed neutrons are injected regularly into a subcritical core. Under the point kinetics model, the number of neutrons in a system at time t , $n(t)$, can be expressed as follows:

$$n(t) = \sum_i a_i \exp(\omega_i t). \quad (1)$$

Immediately after the injection, the behavior of the number of neutrons can be described by a single exponential function as follows:

$$n(t) \simeq C \exp(-\alpha t), \quad (2)$$

where α is the prompt neutron decay constant. The prompt mode is defined as the rapid change in the number of neutrons due to $-\alpha$, while the delayed mode is defined as the comparatively slow change due to ω_i other than $-\alpha$. The prompt neutron decay constant can be transformed into reactivity ρ by using the following equation:

$$\rho \simeq \frac{(\beta - l\alpha)}{(1 - l\alpha)\beta'} \quad (3)$$

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where β is the delayed neutron fraction and l is the prompt neutron lifetime. Thus, the reactivity can be estimated by measuring the number of neutrons immediately after the neutron injection.

However, in fact, there is a possibility that measured prompt neutron decay constant is contaminated by delayed modes. In that case, the reactivity would not be evaluated accurately. To numerically investigate this contamination, the six-group delayed neutron precursor model would be inefficient because the shortest half-life of the precursor groups (or families) is longer than the half-lives of some actual fission products relevant to delayed neutron emission. In the Explicit Fission Product (EFP) model[2], all fission products including extremely short half-lived ones are explicitly treated. The purpose of the present study is to numerically evaluate the delayed neutron contamination in prompt neutron decay constant with the EFP model.

2. NUCLEAR REACTOR KINETICS MODEL

2.1. Six-Group Delayed Neutron Precursor Model

The six-group delayed neutron precursor model[3] is commonly used in reactor kinetics calculations. In this model, fission products are categorized into six precursor groups according to their half-lives. The transmutations among different precursor groups are not considered. We have the reactor kinetics equations with the six-group delayed neutron precursor model as follows:

$$\frac{dn(t)}{dt} = \frac{(1 - \beta)k - 1}{l} n(t) + \sum_{i=1}^6 \lambda_i C_i(t) + S(t), \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{dC_i(t)}{dt} = \frac{\beta_i k}{l} n(t) - \lambda_i C_i(t), \quad (i = 1, \dots, 6), \quad (5)$$

where $C_i(t)$ is the number of the i -th group delayed neutron precursors; $S(t)$ is an external neutron source at time t ; k is neutron multiplication factor; λ_i and β_i are decay constant and delayed neutron fraction of the delayed neutron precursor group i .

2.2. EFP Model

The EFP model treats all fission products including extremely short half-lived ones like Co-77 whose half-life is approximately 0.011 seconds. In addition, transmutations among different FPs are considered. Thus, it is expected that the EFP model can precisely simulate the delayed modes that possibly contaminate the prompt neutron decay constant. We have the reactor kinetics equations with the EFP model as follows:

$$\frac{dn(t)}{dt} = \frac{k_p - 1}{l} n(t) + \sum_{i=1}^I \lambda_i C_i(t) q_i + S(t), \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{dC_i(t)}{dt} = \frac{k_p y_i}{l v_p} n(t) - \lambda_i C_i(t) + \sum_{j=1}^I \lambda_j C_j(t) P_{ji}, \quad (i = 1, \dots, I), \quad (7)$$

where k_p is prompt neutron multiplication factor defined as $k_p = (1 - \beta)k$; v_p is the average number of prompt neutrons by a fission reaction; q_i and y_i are the expected number of emitted neutrons per one decay

and fission yield of nuclide i ; P_{ji} is a transmutation probability in decay from nuclide j to nuclide i ; l is the total number of FPs in the model.

2.3. Numerical Procedure

Both these two models were solved numerically by the following procedure. The reactor kinetics equations with the EFP model can be written in a matrix form as follows:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{x}(t)}{dt} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{k_p - 1}{l} & \lambda_1 q_1 & \lambda_2 q_2 & \cdots & \lambda_l q_l \\ \frac{k_p y_1}{l v_p} & -\lambda_1 & \lambda_2 P_{21} & \cdots & \lambda_l P_{l1} \\ \frac{k_p y_2}{l v_p} & \lambda_1 P_{12} & -\lambda_2 & \cdots & \lambda_l P_{l2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \frac{k_p y_l}{l v_p} & \lambda_1 P_{1l} & \lambda_2 P_{2l} & \cdots & -\lambda_l \end{pmatrix} \mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(t), \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(t) = (n(t) \ C_1(t) \ C_2(t) \ \cdots \ C_l(t))^T$. The solution to Eq. (8) can be formally written as

$$\mathbf{x}(t + \Delta t) = \exp(\mathbf{A}\Delta t) \mathbf{x}(t). \quad (9)$$

In the present study, the matrix exponential $\exp(\mathbf{A}\Delta t)$ was calculated with the mini-max polynomial approximation method[4–5]. As shown in [5], MMPA is guaranteed to be accurate as long as the real part of the eigenvalues of matrix \mathbf{A} is negative, so sufficient accuracy is guaranteed for this problem.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

3.1. Problem Specification

Reactivity measurement with the pulsed neutron source method was simulated with the EFP model and the six-group delayed neutron precursor model. The conditions of this numerical experiment are as follows: the calculation time width Δt is 0.0001 s; the prompt neutron lifetime l is 0.000015 s; the delayed neutron fraction β is 0.0065 for each model; there are no precursors or fission products at the beginning; the reactor core has a reactivity of -0.5 \$; fission of uranium-235 induced by thermal neutrons is assumed.

The parameters of the EFP model are based on JENDL fission product decay data file 2011 and JENDL fission yields data file 2011[6]. The total number of considered fission products is 1284. The constants given in [7] were used in the six-group delayed neutron precursor model.

The reference prompt neutron decay constant was obtained as 648.8 [1/s] by performing the eigenvalue decomposition of \mathbf{A} defined with the EFP model. The corresponding reactivity is -0.501\$.

3.2. Possibility of Delayed Mode Contamination

The prompt neutron decay constant α was obtained through fitting of the number of neutrons after the pulsed neutron injection using the equation $n(t) \simeq C \exp(-\alpha t) + D$. The prompt neutron decay constant obtained from $n(t)$ in different time intervals are shown in Table I. The prompt neutron decay constant

obtained from $n(t)$ between 0.1 ms and 1 ms was 648.3 [1/s] and the reactivity was -0.500 \$, which is almost equal to the reference. As the time interval used for fitting becomes far from the neutron injection, the errors in the estimated prompt neutron decay constant and the reactivity increase, and this is caused by the contamination of the delayed modes. However, when the fitting is carried out for $n(t)$ between 1 ms and 10 ms, the estimated prompt decay constant and the reactivity were 646.1 [1/s] and -0.494 \$, whose difference to the reference is just 0.007 \$. Although the prompt neutron decay constant is slightly contaminated by the delayed mode, the error is practically negligible. Even though the contamination by the delayed modes is insignificant, it would be interesting to investigate whether this comes from delayed modes relevant to the extremely short half-lived fission products in the EFP model. This is going to be investigated in the following section.

Table I. Reactivity estimation with different time intervals.

	0.1~1ms	1~3ms	1~5ms	1~10ms
α [1/s]	648.3	647.5	646.9	646.1
Reactivity[\$]	-0.500	-0.498	-0.496	-0.494

3.3. Comparison with Six-Group Delayed Neutron Precursor Model

In the six-group delayed neutron precursor model, the shortest half-life of the precursor groups is 0.2 seconds, which is longer than those of fission products in the EFP model. By performing the eigenvalue decomposition of \mathbf{A} , ω_i can be obtained. In Figure 1, the relationship between reactivity and ω_i is shown on the left side for the EFP model and on the right side for the six-group delayed neutron precursor model.

Figure 1. Reactivity vs omega plot for the EFP model (left) and the six-group delayed neutron precursor model (right).

The $-\alpha$ corresponding to the prompt mode appears as the leftmost line, and the other lines correspond to delayed modes. While the prompt and delayed modes are clearly separated in the six-group delayed neutron precursor model, the delayed-mode components appear closer to the prompt-mode component in the EFP model. By comparing the results of numerical experiments between the six-

group delayed neutron precursor model and the EFP model, we investigated whether the contamination by delayed modes originates from nuclides with extremely short half-lives.

The constants used in the six-group delayed neutron precursor model are based on the experimental data whereas the parameters in the EFP model are based on the evaluated data given in the nuclear data files. Thus, there is possibly an inconsistency in the constants/parameters between these two models. To ensure consistency between these two models, we adjusted λ_i , q_i , and y_i in the EFP model through the generalized least-square method to reproduce the same delayed neutron emission rate after a single fission reaction with the same procedure in our previous work[8]. Figure 2 shows the delayed neutron emission rate after a single fission reaction with the six-group delayed neutron precursor model, the original EFP model, and the adjusted EFP model. As a result of this, the delayed neutron emission rate as a function of time after a single fission reaction shows good agreement between the adjusted EFP model and the six-group delayed neutron precursor model.

Figure 2. Delayed neutron emission rate after a single fission reaction.

The numerical experiments of the reactivity measurement with the pulsed neutron source method were carried out with the six-group delayed neutron precursor model and the adjusted EFP model. Figure 3 shows the number of neutrons with time after the neutron source injection, and Table II shows the estimated reactivity where each result of α was derived from the number of neutrons in the time interval between 1 ms and 10 ms. The reactivities obtained with the adjusted EFP model and the six-group delayed neutron precursor model agree with each other. Based on this result, it can be said that the delayed mode which affects the prompt neutron decay constant is likely to be derived from nuclides with half-life of 0.2 seconds because the half-life of the shortest half-lived group of the six-group delayed neutron precursor model is 0.2 seconds. Another comparison, based on table II, was made between the adjusted EFP model and the EFP model with the original parameters, and these results also agree with each other. This suggests that the parameter adjustment for the consistency in the parameters/constants does not affect the above conclusion.

Figure 3. Result of numerical experiment with the six-group delayed neutron precursor model and the adjusted EFP model.

Table II. Summary of reactivity estimation.

	$\alpha[1/s]$	Reactivity[\$]
Six-group model	646.2	-0.495
Original EFP model	646.1	-0.494
Adjusted EFP model	646.8	-0.496

3.4. Discussion on the Model Difference

In this subsection, we investigate the reason why the results with the EFP model and the six-group delayed neutron precursor model agreed with each other. Here we define a function and two quantities as follows:

$f(t, t')$: delayed neutron emission rate at t when one fission reaction occurred at t' ,

$F(t')$: fission reaction rate at t' , and

$g(t)$: delayed neutron emission rate at t .

By using $f(t, t')$, the delayed neutron emission rate at t due to fission products generated during $t' \sim t' + dt'$ can be expressed as $F(t')dt'f(t, t')$. By integrating this from 0 to t regarding t' , the delayed neutron emission rate at t , $g(t)$, can be obtained as follows:

$$g(t) = \int_0^t F(t')f(t, t')dt'. \quad (10)$$

Moreover, the fission rate at t' can be expressed as

$$F(t') = \Sigma_f \phi(t') = \Sigma_f V n(t') = \Sigma_f \frac{1}{\Sigma_a t} n(t') = \frac{1}{v l} \frac{v \Sigma_f}{\Sigma_a} n(t') = \frac{k}{v l} n(t') = \frac{1}{v \Lambda} n(t'), \quad (11)$$

where ϕ is the neutron flux; V is the neutron velocity; Λ is the neutron generation time. Based on the above discussions, the following equation for $n(t)$ can be derived:

$$\frac{dn(t)}{dt} = \frac{(1 - \beta)k - 1}{l} n(t) + g(t) + S(t) = \frac{(1 - \beta)k - 1}{l} n(t) + \frac{1}{v\Lambda} \int_0^t n(t')f(t, t')dt' + S(t). \quad (12)$$

Since the time evolution of the number of neutrons, $n(t)$, is governed by $f(t, t')$ and several given parameters, it can be said that the models with the same $f(t, t')$ yield the same behavior of the number of neutrons with time. The delayed neutron emission rate after a single fission reaction corresponds to $f(t, 0)$, which is shown in Fig. 2. Therefore, the behaviors of $n(t)$ obtained with these two models agree with each other because $f(t, t')$ are almost identical in the concerned time period. The discussion implies that this conclusion does not change with other kinetics models if $f(t, t')$ is identical.

In the case of the six-group delayed neutron precursor model, the number of precursors of the group i at time t generated by one fission reaction at t' , $\widehat{C}_i(t, t')$, can be written as $\widehat{C}_i(t, t') = v\beta_i e^{-\lambda_i(t-t')}$, and thus the delayed neutron emission rate at t can be written as follows:

$$f(t, t') = \sum_i \lambda_i \widehat{C}_i(t, t') = \sum_i \lambda_i v\beta_i e^{-\lambda_i(t-t')}. \quad (13)$$

Thus, $g(t)$ is represented as

$$g(t) = \int_0^t F(t')f(t, t')dt' = \int_0^t \frac{1}{v\Lambda} n(t') \sum_i \lambda_i v\beta_i e^{-\lambda_i(t-t')} dt' = \int_0^t n(t') \sum_i \frac{\lambda_i \beta_i}{\Lambda} e^{-\lambda_i(t-t')} dt'. \quad (14)$$

This expression can also be derived mathematically as follows. Let us focus on the kinetics equation for precursor of group i and apply the Laplace transform:

$$\frac{dC_i(t)}{dt} = -\lambda_i C_i(t) + \frac{\beta_i}{\Lambda} n(t), \quad (15)$$

$$sC_i(s) - C(0) = -\lambda_i C_i(s) + \frac{\beta_i}{\Lambda} n(s). \quad (16)$$

By applying $C(0) = 0$ and rearranging, we obtain the following equation:

$$C_i(s) = \frac{\beta_i}{\Lambda(s + \lambda_i)} n(s). \quad (17)$$

Applying the inverse Laplace transform of the convolution to this, we obtain the following equation:

$$C_i(t) = \frac{\beta_i}{\Lambda} \int_0^t n(t') e^{-\lambda_i(t-t')} dt'. \quad (18)$$

The delayed neutron emission rate of group i at t can be described as

$$\lambda_i C_i(t) = \frac{\lambda_i \beta_i}{\Lambda} \int_0^t n(t') e^{-\lambda_i(t-t')} dt'. \quad (19)$$

Thus, we obtain the delayed neutron emission rate of all precursor group as follows:

$$\sum_i \lambda_i C_i(t) = g(t) = \int_0^t n(t') \sum_i \frac{\lambda_i \beta_i}{\Lambda} e^{-\lambda_i(t-t')} dt'. \quad (20)$$

This is exactly the same as Eq. (14).

4. CONCLUSION

We investigated whether the prompt neutron decay constant measured in experiments is contaminated by delayed modes. Through numerical experiments, it was found that although the prompt neutron decay constant is slightly contaminated by the delayed mode, the error is practically negligible. To investigate the origin of delayed mode, we compared the numerical results of the six-group delayed neutron precursor model and the EFP model. The comparison indicates that the delayed mode contaminating prompt neutron decay constant is likely to be derived from nuclides with half-life of 0.2 seconds. We also found that the models based on the same delayed neutron emission rate after a single fission reaction yield the same behavior of the number of neutrons.

The six-group delayed neutron precursor model is not completely consistent with the EFP model. In future work, if the six-group delayed neutron precursor model that treats nuclear transmutation is developed and it becomes consistent with the EFP model, it can help precise kinetics calculation with low calculation cost.

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